

LANGUAGE EVOLUTION AND LANGUAGE ECONOMY

Saidov Khayrulla Shavkatovich

Bukhara State University, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Abstract. Language economy is a universal category inherent in all languages of the world, characterized by the desire to save energy, avoid excessive expenditure of physiological and psychological effort when using speech and manifests itself at all levels of the language system. The principle of economy is expressed in the creation and perception of language elements with minimal effort and can be considered one of the reasons for language changes.

Keywords: the principle of economy, qualitative reduction, tendency to redundancy, cognitive categories, linguistic compression, loss of aspiration

ЯЗЫКОВАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ И ЯЗЫКОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА

Саидов Хайрулла Шавкатович,

Бухарский государственный университет, Бухара, Узбекистан

Аннотация. Языковая экономия – универсальная категория, присущая всем языкам мира, характеризующаяся стремлением к экономии энергии, избеганию чрезмерной затраты физиологических и психологических усилий при использовании речи и проявляющаяся на всех уровнях языковой системы. Принцип экономии выражается в создании и восприятии языковых элементов с минимальными усилиями и может считаться одной из причин языковых изменений.

Ключевые слова: принцип экономии, качественная редукция, склонность к избыточности, когнитивные категории, языковая компрессия, потеря аспирации.

The tendency to save language resources is one of the internal factors contributing to the development and improvement of the language, which, according to many linguists, is universal and affects all levels of the language system. It is proved that economy proceeds differently at different levels of language (phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic, etc.), being an internal driving force in language evolution.

The principle of language economy is reflected in the ability to express the diversity of the objective world in an economical way [4;57]. Language is the main form that reflects our knowledge of the world, as well as the main means of storing, processing and transmitting knowledge. The most well-known cognitive categories borrowed from knowledge representation theory include the concepts of frame and scenario. Frames and prototypes are among the most well-known categories borrowed from knowledge representation theory [6;65].

Language is a dynamic and constantly evolving system that is characterized by variability and dynamism. At the same time, we should not ignore the unevenness in the historical development of individual language levels, the non-uniformity and heterogeneity of changes occurring in them, which are caused by the action of both external and internal factors [3;143]. One of these internal factors that contribute to the development and improvement of the language is the tendency to save language resources, which, according to many linguists, is universal and affects all levels of the language system [9;38]. The history of language economy has a long tradition.

It has been addressed by various thinkers, starting with Aristotle. Systematic study of the principle of economy in language should be associated with research in the field of phonetics and, above all, with the names of such linguists as H.Sweet, P.Passy, V.Whitney, who indicated the presence of two opposite trends in the language: the tendency to facilitate pronunciation and its opposite – the tendency to redundancy [10;12].

A. Martine initiated the study of economy in the field of phonology, expanding the scope of this principle and giving economy a universal character,

considering it the cause of phonetic changes [5;58]. In modern linguistics, there are two approaches to understanding the principle of economy: broad (any phenomenon in synchrony and diachrony that leads to the disappearance of new forms and contributes to the improvement of language as a means of communication) and narrow (quantitative, based on the variability of language means, that is, replacing them with more economical units). A broad understanding is characteristic of language as a system, and a narrow understanding is characteristic of speech.

Conversational speech is the main area of implementation of language economy. Colloquial speech is also reflected in fiction for a more realistic description of the life of a certain environment, to create a verbal portrait of a particular character [1;417]. The language of journalism and science is also not alien to elements of colloquial speech.

The principle of economy in language and speech is universal, due to its penetration into all levels of economy: on the phonetic level (the contraction and omission of phonemes), the lexical (substitution of single word phrases, shortening of words, merge the words into one lexical unit), on morphological (the use of synthetic forms is analytical; the conversion of nouns, adjectives, and participles; the omission or reduction affixes) and syntactic levels (using elliptical sentences) [8;302].

Despite the variety of names, the essence of language economy is as follows: language economy is a universal category inherent in all languages of the world, characterized by the desire to save energy, avoid excessive expenditure of physiological and psychological effort when using speech and manifests itself at all levels of the language system.

It is believed that the human mind has a unique technique of mental perception of information. This psychotechnics regulates the understanding of information at all levels of the language, which comes from the environment in a "compressed" form. Understanding information also occurs at the phonemic level of the language, since the phoneme has a social aspect and performs the functions of

distinguishing significant units of speech. However, it does not have its own meaning, and is implemented in one of the sounds of the morpheme. The fact that the number of phonemes is limited (if there is a natural personal differentiation associated with the physiological characteristics of the speaker), allows for the unification of sounds to the extent of their full understanding. Thus, any phoneme of the language can be described as phonocentrism.

At the second level of the language, word-forming and form-forming morphemes are combined. These morphemes in the language are also limited, that is why during the formation of entirely new word forms or words the language user can understand and even "feel" the semantics of these entities and, ultimately, to reduce language to a limited number of morphemes.

In various spheres, compression has a specific character that is peculiar only to this circle, which reflects the stylistic difference in the language (with certain features and rules of use). Since the natural need of a person is his need for communication, it is natural for him to strive to save language resources.

Another example of sound modification in speech is reduction, which results in weakening and changing the sound of unstressed syllables. Reduction is the historical process of weakening and disappearing vowel sounds.

It is believed that the inertia of the speech tract is the main factor in the presence of vowel reduction. The vowel reduction occurs in the weak positions of prosodic or morphological, in particular, unstressed syllables and affixes.

Reduction of English vowel sounds is a change in sounds, the cause of which is their unstressed position in relation to other sounds, i.e., any unstressed vowel sound can be reduced in one way or another. In English, there is a reduction of only vowel sounds, in Uzbek both vowels and consonants [11;98].

In unstressed syllables, vowels are reduced, meaning that long vowel sounds are shortened, and short vowels can be replaced with the sound [ə]. There is a quantitative and qualitative reduction [a: – a – ə].

In addition to non-elementary syllables, this phonetic phenomenon is usually used in auxiliary words such as pronouns, auxiliary verbs, modal verbs, and in non-elementary positions. For example:

beautiful ['bju:təf(ə)l];

we must do it at once ['wi: məst 'du: it ət 'wʌns].

Now let's look at the cases with aspiration. In the percussive position, the consonants [p, t, k] are pronounced with aspiration. For example: *pie* ['phaɪ].

As for the loss of aspiration, it should be noted that in the percussive position, the consonants [p, t, k] in the combinations [s + p, s + t, s + k] are pronounced without aspiration. For example: *start* ['sta:t]

In English, as in Uzbek, only to an even greater extent, the pronunciation of a vowel sound in a stressed syllable differs strongly and distinctly, and in an unstressed syllable – weakly, with the loss of sound characteristics (qualitative reduction), sometimes with a reduction in its longitude (quantitative reduction). The final stage of sound reduction is its complete loss from the spoken word (zero reduction). Cf. OE. *stāne* [sta:ne] – ME *stone* [stone] – ModE *stone* [stoun].

The process of qualitative reduction of vowels in an unstressed syllable led to the emergence of a neutral sound, which replaced all other vowel sounds, except the phoneme [i] [7;102]

As a result of reduction, most English auxiliary words have two forms of pronunciation: full (stressed) and reduced (both forms are represented in transcriptions of English dictionaries).

Full forms are used in the percussive position, and reduced forms are used in the unstressed position. This applies primarily to all auxiliary words – articles, link and modal verbs, conjunctions and prepositions, as well as often to personal and possessive pronouns, and adverbs. In the unstressed position (and this is almost always the case), they are pronounced in a weak form, individual sounds become shorter and less distinct. A speech in which all the words are pronounced accurately and clearly will sound completely unnatural [2;73].

For example, (in transcription, the first form is full, the second is reduced):

Articles: **a** [e, ə], **an** [æ, ə], **the** [ðj, ði, ðə];

Prepositions: **of** [ɒv, əv], **for** [fɒ, fə], **too** [th, tu, tə], etc;

Conjunctions: **and** [ænd, ənd], **but** [bʌt, bət], **that** [ðæt, ðət], etc.

Quantitative reduction is typical for long vowel sounds. For example, the pronoun **me** is pronounced under the stress of [mj], and in the unstressed position in fluent speech [mi].

Zero reduction is also reflected in the letter: instead of the letter that falls out and expresses a sound in full form, an apostrophe is put: I'm late. [aim leit].

Thus, all unstressed words: articles, prepositions, conjunctions, particles, etc. – are pronounced together (merged) with the stressed word with which they are related in meaning, and vowel sounds are reduced in them [12;56]. For example, a merged pronunciation of a notional verb followed by a personal pronoun:

I 'see him [ai'sjhim].

You 'help her [ju'helphə:].

The noun and the preposition related to it (prepositional group) are pronounced together, without a break of breath: **to** facts [tə'fæktz], **for** tents [fə'tents], **of** tests [əv'tests]. But if the preposition is at the end of a sentence or before an unstressed personal pronoun at the end of a sentence, it retains the full, though unstressed, form: Look **at** them ['luk æt ðəm].

The definite article is pronounced as [ðə] or [ði] – before words beginning with a vowel: **the** step [ðə'step], to **the** end [tə ði'end], the indefinite article **a(an)** is pronounced as a neutral sound [ə (ən)]: a plan [ə'plæn], an oak [ən'ouk].

If the first of two adjacent words has the final letter **r**, and the next one begins with **a** vowel, then when reading they are connected by the sound [r], which helps to pronounce the two vowels together: *for a plan* [fərə'plæn], *for a mile* [fərə'mail].

The conjunction **and** [ənd] is pronounced very briefly, without stress and merged, in the same breath, with the words that it connects: *a reader and a writer* [ə'ri:dərənd ə'raitə].

Examples prove that it is the cognitive structures in human verbal thinking that cause phonetic economy in each act of speech of communicants.

Thus, the tendency to save language resources is due to the needs of human thinking and communication. The principle of language economy is reflected in the ability to express the diversity of the objective world in an economical way. Language is the main form that reflects our knowledge of the world, as well as the main means of storing, processing and transmitting knowledge. The most well-known cognitive categories borrowed from knowledge representation theory include the concepts of frame and scenario. Frames and prototypes are among the most well-known categories borrowed from knowledge representation theory [13].

In conclusion, we emphasize that the recognition by linguists of the fact of processing phonetic and phonological information using non-linguistic mental operations of cognitive computing, even more strongly dictates the need for further cognitive research in the field of phonetics and phonology of speech activity.

1. Arutyunova N.D. Rech // Russkiy yazyk. Ensiklopedya (Speech //Russian language. Encyclopedia). M., 1997. -P. 417.
2. Budagov R.A. Problemy razvitiya yazyka (Problems of language development). – M.-L.:Nauka, 1965. – p.73.
3. Bushuy A. M. Yasyk I deystvitelnost (Language and Reality). – Tashkent: Fan, 2005. – 144p.
4. Jespersen O. Philosophy of Grammar. – University of Chicago Press, 1992. – 372p.
5. Martine A. Principle of economy in phonetic changes: Problems of diachronic phonology. M.: Inostrannaya literature, 1960. -301p.
6. Maslova V.A. Kognitivnaya lingvistika: uchebnoye posobiye (Cognitive linguistics: manual. Minsk: Tetra Systems, 2008. – 272p.
7. Paul H. Principles of the History of Language. – Alpha Editions, 2019. – 584 p.

8. Serebrennikov B.A. Poblema progressa v razbitii // Obsheyee yazikoznaniye (The Problem of Progress in the Development of Languages // General linguistics). Moscow: Nauka, 1970, pp. 302-307.
9. Paul, Hermann. Deutsche Grammatik. Vieter Band. – Halle (Saale): Max Niemeyer Verlag, 1958. – 425 p.
10. Sweet H. The Sounds of English. An Introduction to Phonetics. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1929.
11. Passy P. Etudes sur les Changements Phonetiques et leurs Caracteres Generaux. Paris: Firmin – Didot, 1891.
12. Whitney W.D. The Life and Growth of Language. An Outline of Linguistic Science. – NY: Appleton and Company, 1897. – 326 p.
13. Zubaydullo Izomovich Rasulov. The problem of language economy from the perspective of language evolution. <http://www.jcreview.com/?mno=9928> [Access: September 14, 2020]. doi:10.31838/jcr.07.17.17.